

The study of requirements for the workforce of the digital industries using web scraping techniques

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates workforce requirements in Thailand's digital industries, focusing on qualification requirements across five industry groups: hardware and smart devices, software and software services, digital service, digital content, and telecommunication. Employing Python-based web scraping from selected job websites during 2022–2023, the data undergoes natural language processing (NLP) for analysis. Within Group 1 (hardware and smart devices), electrical engineers dominate with 92 positions, emphasizing a demand for engineering expertise. Group 2 (software and software services) sees a surge in programmer roles, totaling 244 positions, showcasing a need for robust programming skills. Group 3 (digital service) prioritizes information technology (IT) support, claiming 354 positions, indicating high demand for IT support qualifications. Graphic design leads Group 4 (digital content) with 587 positions, highlighting the need for a workforce in digital content production. In Group 5 (telecommunication), network engineers dominate with 37 positions, signaling a demand for top-tier network engineering skills. Most positions across groups specify a bachelor's degree and often require prior experience, highlighting the industry's preference for both academic and practical qualifications. This study underscores the digital industry's rapid growth and the sustained demand for a qualified workforce, emphasizing the importance of academic credentials and specialized skills for future employment in these sectors.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The digital industry, often referred to as industry 4.0, encompasses businesses engaged in the production, distribution, and provision of services related to digital technology, leveraging its advancements. This sector not only plays a pivotal role in propelling the economy but also contributes significantly to the evolution of a digital society [1]. Crucially, the digital industry holds a strategic position in the government's vision for Thailand's economic development and is identified as one of the 10 target industries (S-Curve). The Ministry of Industry has specifically earmarked the digital industry as a key player in steering the nation towards a digital economy, anticipating substantial shifts in investment dynamics [2]. Furthermore, it actively aligns with the government's initiatives in formulating policies for digital labor, aiming to usher in transformative changes in the labor system [3]. However, the advent of digital transformation poses a substantial hiring challenge. This stems from the transformative nature of change, which may usher in new

roles to replace old ones or render some jobs obsolete. Work dynamics that once followed familiar patterns must adapt to change as operational modes become fortified by technology. Notably, the encroachment of machines into tasks once performed by humans is increasingly evident, creating a surge in demand for labor equipped with new skills across various industries [4].

In the digital industry, this demand for skilled labor is particularly pronounced. Entrepreneurs recognize the paramount importance of aligning workers' skills with organizational needs. Employees are expected not only to possess skills that correspond to their job roles but also to continually enhance and adapt their skill sets. This is especially pertinent in the digital industry, where positions such as programmers, developers, system administrators, information technology (IT) system analysts, website designers, and developers remain consistently high in demand [3]. The evolving landscape of the digital industry underscores the necessity for a workforce equipped with dynamic and relevant skills.

Despite the escalating trend of technology replacing human labor, the digital industry continues to present numerous job opportunities. The abundance of job postings on recruitment and general advertisement websites, with over 10 such websites in Thailand alone, showcasing tens of thousands of related job positions, serves as evidence of this [5]. This abundance suggests a sustained and growing demand for workers in the digital industry. Furthermore, job websites serve as easy-to-access platforms for job seekers to explore potential opportunities. These web pages provide detailed information that workers can use to make informed decisions about applying for positions. Simultaneously, these platforms offer employers an effective means of leveraging digital media to disseminate recruitment information. The convenience of online systems also facilitates the streamlined assessment of labor qualifications, eliminating the need for physical visits to apply for positions an efficiency that contributes to cost savings for both employers and job seekers [6]. Even though job recruitment websites specify job titles and the skills or requirements for each position, workers may not be able to determine which job positions and skill sets are most in demand in the digital industry.

Web scraping is the process of using automated scripts to extract data from websites. This method is often used to gather publicly available information but not easily downloadable in a structured format, such as pricing data, contact details, or textual content from web pages [7]. The research by Lunn *et al.* [8] utilizes web scraping and natural language processing (NLP) to study the clear necessities for job applicants, highlighting the in-demand programming skills. This demonstrates that web scraping is beneficial for drawing inferences from large amounts of data. Furthermore, we can employ NLP to reliably extract key information from text. The study by Schedlbauer *et al.* [9] examined the labor market in medical informatics using web scraping to gather data. It highlighted the most frequently found terms, such as programming, experience, projects, and servers. Additionally, it found that 45% of the vocabulary indicates a demand for expert skills, while 55% reflects a demand for soft skills. Research such as that conducted by Priya *et al.* [10] has utilized web scraping to extract data from job portals, enabling a detailed analysis of the job market and the most sought-after skills, as well as those required for specific roles. This information can assist job seekers in better understanding the job market and the skills required to increase their employability. Employers are seeking graduates with skills in emotional intelligence, communication, IT/computer proficiency, problem-solving, analytical abilities, and teamwork capabilities, according to research by MacKenzie [11], which analyzed job descriptions gathered through web scraping. Web scraping also collects job postings from multiple websites and consolidates them on a single platform, thereby enhancing the browsing experience for visitors. This helps reduce the time and complexity involved in searching for information [12]. Additionally, web scraping is used to extract real-time job vacancy data, ensuring that job seekers do not miss out on interesting positions, and it can also suggest skills that workers could improve to enhance their employability [13]. The research also shows how developing potential job search engines using web scraping tools and machine learning techniques can streamline the process of finding jobs that align with job seekers' interests [14].

The burgeoning digital industry is creating a myriad of opportunities and attracting significant investments, resulting in a substantial demand for related job positions. However, this surge in demand necessitates a workforce with specific skills, knowledge (hard skills), abilities, and competencies tailored to each position's requirements. Moreover, while the trend toward digital workplaces presents numerous opportunities for both employers and employees, it also poses clear challenges that require collaborative efforts to overcome. Business leaders will face intense competition when hiring and retaining the best talent. Keeping track of labor market trends related to technology and digital skills will be crucial [15]. As a response to this dynamic landscape, studying related research revealed a research gap in the analysis of the digital industry across the five main industrial sectors, as well as a deficiency in the presentation of job titles that align with the demands of each sector. Thus, this research aims to present comprehensive job requirements and qualifications for individuals entering the labor market in the digital industry, both in the current and future contexts. We collect data from job advertisement websites using web scraping techniques, then extract and process the information using NLP methods to obtain the desired knowledge. The aim is

twofold: first, to provide a guiding framework for those pursuing education in relevant fields of study, enabling them to align their skills with industry needs. Second, it serves as crucial information for existing and prospective workers, aiding them in understanding and developing competencies that harmonize with the evolving operations of the digital industry. This research offers a roadmap for skill development and seeks to contribute to the ongoing enhancement of the workforce in this dynamic and pivotal sector.

2. RELATED WORKS

In this section, the study delves into pertinent literature addressing two focal points central to the core objectives of this research: firstly, the dynamic and ever-evolving landscape of the digital industry, highlighting key trends, challenges, and opportunities that shape its development. Secondly, it examines the increasingly critical role of web scraping as a strategic tool for data collection and analysis within this sector, emphasizing its effectiveness in gathering vast amounts of real-time data. The literature review underscores the importance of adapting to technological advancements and the necessity for innovative methodologies in navigating the complexities of the digital industry. Furthermore, it explores how web scraping contributes to more accurate and comprehensive insights, ultimately informing better decision-making processes.

2.1. The digital industry

This segment scrutinizes existing literature on the digital industry, recognizing it as a pivotal force shaping contemporary life within the digital economy era. It explores the profound impact of emerging technologies on the digital market, highlighting the dynamic nature of digital industrialization that evolves in tandem with technological advancements. The digital industry, encompassing both manufacturing and service sectors, is intricately linked to digital technology utilization. The study categorizes this utilization into five principal groups [16], elucidating the multifaceted dimensions of its influence.

2.1.1. Hardware and smart devices

Focused on the publication and distribution of computer devices, this industry includes smart devices, computer memory, office devices, and implements for the internet of things (IoT), as well as robotics devices. This sector is critical as it drives technological advancements and innovation across various applications, from consumer electronics to industrial automation. The proliferation of IoT and smart technologies is particularly transformative, enhancing connectivity and efficiency in both everyday life and complex industrial systems. As such, the development and distribution of these devices play a pivotal role in shaping future technological landscapes and enabling smarter, more connected environments.

2.1.2. Software and software services

This sector revolves around the creation and dissemination of software products and services. Examples include computer software, data processing software, device control software, and office application software. It serves as the backbone of modern technology infrastructure, providing essential tools for businesses, governments, and consumers to operate efficiently in a digital world. The impact of this sector is widespread, influencing productivity, communication, and data management across all industries. As technology continues to advance, the role of software products and services becomes increasingly vital in enabling innovation and supporting complex systems and processes.

2.1.3. Digital service

This industry provides digital advisory services on digital platforms, such as cloud computing, system maintenance, and IT support. It plays a crucial role in enabling businesses to leverage advanced technologies to improve their operational efficiency, scalability, and security. The focus on cloud computing allows organizations of all sizes to access powerful computing resources and data storage solutions without significant capital investment. Additionally, system maintenance and IT support ensure that these digital systems function optimally, addressing technical issues and preventing downtime. This sector is essential for supporting businesses' digital transformation and helping them adapt to the rapidly changing technological landscape.

2.1.4. Digital content

This sector is engaged in the production, distribution, and service of digital content, which includes computer graphics, animation, digital games, e-books, user interface (UX) or user experience (UI) design, and new media in augmented reality (AR) or virtual reality (VR) formats. This sector is at the forefront of entertainment, education, and marketing innovations, blending creativity with technology to create immersive and engaging experiences for users. Advanced technologies like AR and VR are revolutionizing content

consumption, providing more interactive and realistic experiences that significantly boost user engagement. This dynamic field not only caters to entertainment but also extends its influence to educational platforms and professional training, making it a pivotal area of growth in the digital economy.

2.1.5. Telecommunication

This industry involves the operation of telecommunications network businesses and services, including cellphone network providers, satellite contract providers, and Internet network service providers. It forms the backbone of global communication, facilitating the seamless flow of information across vast distances. By providing critical infrastructure for voice, data, and video transmission, this sector enables both individuals and businesses to connect and communicate effectively, regardless of location. The importance of telecommunications networks has grown exponentially with the digital revolution, supporting everything from everyday mobile communications to complex, cloud-based business solutions. As technology continues to advance, the role of these networks in enabling new forms of digital interaction, such as IoT applications and smart cities, becomes increasingly crucial.

2.2. Web scraping

A data science technique for extracting information from the internet, web scraping, can be executed using packaged software or directly through a programming language. Python, renowned for its efficacy in handling and analyzing large datasets, emerges as the most prevalent programming language for this purpose and is the chosen tool for data collection in this study. The BeautifulSoup library, equipped with user-friendly Python scripts for web scraping, facilitates a streamlined process. This approach allows researchers to efficiently gather and process web data, which is crucial for various analytical applications, thereby enhancing the robustness and depth of research findings.

Python's simplicity allows for concise code creation in just a few steps, making it ideal for data collection and analysis. The process involves importing the necessary library, rendering the web page, establishing storage variables, and extracting and cleaning the data. Once completed, the collected information is stored in a preferred format; in this research, the CSV and Excel file formats are the chosen mediums [7]. This approach ensures efficient and accessible data collection and analysis, aligning perfectly with the study's objectives. Python's ability to work seamlessly with data, coupled with libraries like Pandas and openpyxl for handling CSV and Excel files, respectively, greatly enhances the productivity and effectiveness of research workflows.

3. METHODS AND MATERIALS

The primary unit of analysis for this study comprises data sourced from job posting and advertisement websites, offering a crucial insight into evolving employment trends and skill demands. The aim is to examine the future workforce requirements in the digital industry, classified into five distinct groups: i) hardware and smart devices, ii) software and software services, iii) digital service, iv) digital content, and v) telecommunication. Contemporary technology, particularly information and communications technology, intricately links each of these industries, reflecting broader economic, and technological transformations. Notably, there is a discernible trend indicating an anticipated increase in demand for workforce requirements in the future, underscoring the urgency for educational institutions and policymakers to adapt and respond to these emerging needs. Figure 1 summarizes the workflow.

Figure 1. Proposed method framework

3.1. Web scraping techniques

Web scraping stands out as an effective technique for data collection from websites, leveraging powerful Python tools. The rationale for choosing this method lies in its versatility and efficiency, allowing researchers to quickly gather and process large volumes of data directly from the source in a programmable and scalable manner. This method not only reduces the manpower and financial resources needed for manual data collection but also enhances the accuracy and comprehensiveness of the data collected, making it invaluable for studies that require up-to-date and detailed information across various fields [17]. The primary steps involved in the data collection process are as follows:

3.1.1. Choose the job advertisement or posting website

The first step is to choose a website that specializes in job advertisements or postings. These websites typically host a plethora of relevant job postings, and identifying suitable platforms is generally straightforward. It is essential to ensure that these sites have a comprehensive and diverse range of listings that reflect the current job market trends in various industries. This approach not only streamlines the collection process but also guarantees that the data extracted is representative and extensive, facilitating a more accurate analysis of workforce requirements and employment opportunities across sectors. However, the criteria for selecting target websites must ensure that they feature job positions related to all five groups within the digital industry. This is crucial to ensure that the data gathered is comprehensive and effectively addresses the analysis of future workforce requirements. Selecting websites that meet this specific criterion helps to ensure that data collection is accurate and current, supporting the research and achieving clearly defined results.

3.1.2. Inspect the URL location

Proceeding to inspect the uniform resource locator (URL) location is crucial. Typically, the URLs on job listing webpages are in hypertext markup language (HTML). Ensuring that these websites do not employ scripts to impede data access is imperative. The inspection process involves utilizing web browser tools, such as the inspect method, to scrutinize the structure of the URL and confirm its accessibility for data extraction. To inspect with Google Chrome, right-click on the webpage and select the "Inspect" command to display the HTML. This step allows researchers to understand the underlying code and navigate potential barriers, such as dynamically loaded content via JavaScript, which can complicate data scraping. Figure 2 illustrates how the inspection window provides a clear view of the webpage's elements, highlighting the structure of data and its location for extraction, thereby facilitating a more targeted and efficient scraping strategy.

Figure 2. Inspecting URL location on a job list

3.1.3. Extracting all URLs

This step uses Python to systematically extract all URLs from the webpage containing job listings. This process uses the bs4 module from the BeautifulSoup library and stores the URL data in a Pandas data

frame [18]. We subsequently export the extracted data to Excel or CSV file formats to facilitate further analysis. Users can conveniently select specific groups of interest directly from the homepage thanks to the common categorization of job positions. Users can further streamline their search by selecting desired job position categories, enhancing the efficiency and precision of the data extraction process. Are visualized in Figure 3.

```

13 # Specify the number of pages you want to scrape
14 num_pages = 14 # Change this to the number of pages you want to scrape
15 for page_number in range(1, num_pages + 1):
16     # Construct the URL for the current page
17     url = base_url + str(page_number)
18
19 # Send an HTTP GET request to the URL
20 response = requests.get(url)
21
22 if response.status_code == 200:
23     # Parse the HTML content of the page
24     soup = BeautifulSoup(response.text, 'html.parser')
25
26 # Find and scrape the data you need from the current page using your existing code
27 # Example: Find 'h1' tags and 'a' tags within 'h1' for each page
28 h1_tags = soup.find_all('h1')
29 for h1 in h1_tags:
30     a_tags = h1.find_all('a')
31     for a in a_tags:
32         job_data.append({
33             "Title": a.text,
34             "URL": a.get('href')
35         })
36 # Print the Title and URL for each job
37 print("Title:", a.text)
38 print("URL:", a.get('href'))
39
40 # Print the page number for reference
41 print("Scraping data from page (page_number)")
42
43 else:
44     print("Failed to retrieve page (page_number). Status code:", response.status_code)
45
46 # Create a Pandas DataFrame from the collected data
47 df = pd.DataFrame(job_data)
48
49 # Insert a new column 'No.' for row numbering
50 df['No.']= range(1, len(df) + 1)
51
52 # Reorder the columns with 'No.' as the first column
53 df = df[['No.', 'Title', 'URL']]
54
55 # Export the DataFrame to an Excel file
56 excel_file_name = "URL-Page-G1-(jobids.com).xlsx"

```

Figure 3. Extracting all URLs for job positions

3.1.4. Inspect the location of desired information

At this point, the focus is on the job title and description webpage, where HTML tags like headings (tag h1-h6), paragraphs (tag p), and lists (tag li) typically contain pertinent information. When inspecting the Google Chrome inspection page, carefully scroll through it to accurately locate the data [19]. It is essential to conduct a thorough examination, as certain tags might have specific IDs or classes, which adds an extra level of scrutiny for precise data extraction. This meticulous inspection ensures the precise location and retrieval of the desired information for comprehensive analysis. As depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Inspecting the location of desired information

3.1.5. Web scraping using Python

For data aggregation, web scraping is a powerful tool that enables the collection and consolidation of information from diverse sources. Gathering vast amounts of data quickly and efficiently, and then

analyzing it to discern patterns, trends, or insights relevant to various industries or fields of study, is particularly effective with this method. At this stage, we execute web scraping using Python, utilizing the BeautifulSoup package library [20]. The extracted data is then exported in Excel file format. The methodology involves the efficient use of URL looping, enabling the simultaneous scraping of data from multiple web pages. This approach is particularly advantageous for handling large datasets, significantly optimizing time utilization [21], [22].

Given that the preceding step yields links to numerous job positions, the resulting text is often a mix of natural language, special characters, numbers, symbols, and other unstructured elements. Consequently, these texts will undergo NLP in the subsequent step to refine and structure the data for comprehensive analysis. This processing involves techniques such as tokenization, the removal of stopwords, and the extraction of key terms, which are essential for filtering out irrelevant information and highlighting significant details relevant to job market trends. As depicted in Figure 5, this step is crucial for converting raw data into a format that is both analyzable and actionable, ensuring that the insights derived are accurate and meaningful.

```

6 # List of URLs you want to scrape
7 urls = []
8 https://th.jobsdb.com/th/en/job/business-system-analyst-300003002955896?token=0-4ef27b61-9c2f-4c69-96f7-271e4d4302
9 https://th.jobsdb.com/th/en/job/senior-flutter-developer-300003002955590?token=0-4ef27b61-9c2f-4c69-96f7-271e4d4302
10 https://th.jobsdb.com/th/en/job/frontend-engineer-application-developer-based-in-bangkok-view-graduate-to-welcome-3000030029
11 https://th.jobsdb.com/th/en/job/devops-engineer-empower-devops-engineer-innovation-300003002951461?token=0-4ef27b61-9c2f-4c69-96f7-271e
12 https://th.jobsdb.com/th/en/job/solutions-developer-servicesnow-300003002947629?token=0-4ef27b61-9c2f-4c69-96f7-271e
13 https://th.jobsdb.com/th/en/job/application-support-30000300295923?token=0-4ef27b61-9c2f-4c69-96f7-271e4d4302
14 https://th.jobsdb.com/th/en/job/senior-application-architect-manufacturing-energy-chemical-30000300294993?token=0-4ef27b61-9c2f-4c69-96f7-271e4d4302
15 https://th.jobsdb.com/th/en/job/software-developer-c-spp-net-vb-net-300003002955708?token=0-4ef27b61-9c2f-4c69-96f7-271e4d4302
16 https://th.jobsdb.com/th/en/job/full-stack-developer-30000300294640?token=0-4ef27b61-9c2f-4c69-96f7-271e4d4302
17 https://th.jobsdb.com/th/en/job/backend-engineer-junior-level-tech-golang-300003002947362?token=0-4ef27b61-9c2f-4c69-96f7-271e4d4302
18 https://th.jobsdb.com/th/en/job/software-engineer-300003002946297?token=0-4ef27b61-9c2f-4c69-96f7-271e4d4302
19 https://th.jobsdb.com/th/en/job/system-analyst-iot-on-site-silom-300003002948090?token=0-4ef27b61-9c2f-4c69-96f7-271e4d4302
20 https://th.jobsdb.com/th/en/job/data-analyst-specialist-software-esp-bom-30000300295272?token=0-4ef27b61-9c2f-4c69-96f7-271e4d4302
21 https://th.jobsdb.com/th/en/job/senior-golang-engineer-300003002951973?token=0-4ef27b61-9c2f-4c69-96f7-271e4d4302
22 https://th.jobsdb.com/th/en/job/system-analyst-16-positions-jwb-c-net-pl-sql-on-site-8rs-ai-300003002953901?token=0-4ef27b61-9c2f-4c69-96f7-271e4d4302
23 https://th.jobsdb.com/th/en/job/senior-qa-manual-test-30000300295516?token=0-4ef27b61-9c2f-4c69-96f7-271e4d4302
24 ]
25
26 # Function to scrape data from a URL
27 def scrape_data(url):
28     # Send an HTTP GET request to the URL
29     response = requests.get(url)
30
31     # Check if the request was successful
32     if response.status_code == 200:
33         # Parse the HTML content of the page using BeautifulSoup
34         soup = BeautifulSoup(response.text, 'html.parser')
35
36     # Extract the h1 element
37     h1_element = soup.find('h1', class_='z15em0o _1bh6w6e4y y44q70 y44q70 _1d09p9k4 y44q70 y44q70i21')
38
39     # Extract div elements
40     div_elements = soup.find_all('div', class_='z15em0o _15139pe0 _5139pe2')
41

```

```

Scraping data from: https://th.jobsdb.com/th/en/job/data-analyst-specialist-software-esp-bom-30000300295272?token=0-4ef27b61-9c2f-4c69-96f7-271e4d4302&section
Job 14
H1 Element Text: Data Analyst Specialist - Software / SAP / BOM
Div Element Text: Job HighlightsGlobal Home Appliance CompanySoftware Engr/Data Analyst/Etc (Senior Level)/Expertise in SAP System, BOM
Div Element Text: Job DescriptionOur client is the world's leading manufacturer and supplier of commercial home appliances. The Data Analyst Specialist will be responsible for
Div Element Text: Additional InformationCareer LevelSeniorQualification(N/A)Years of Experience(N/A)Job TypePermanentCompany Websitehttp://www.ptc.com.th FunctionsInf
Div Element Text: Company OverviewMore than just a recruitment company. At PRTR, we have been a part of our customer's success for 30 years as their total HR solutions p
to develop a better career, a better life, and a better society, and thrive to become the No.1 people solutions organization in Southeast Asia.
http://www.ptc.com
PRTR | Thailand's Leading Provider of Total HR Solutions.
Div Element Text: Additional Company InformationIndustryHuman Resources Management/Consultancy
Div Element Text: Browse JobsPost resumesJob alertsProfileCareer adviceExplore careersExplore salariesDownload appsJobsDB @ App StoreJobsDB @ Google Play
Div Element Text: JobsDB @ App StoreJobsDB @ Google Play
Div Element Text: Post a job adSearch candidatesadvertise with usBest companies
Div Element Text: About JobsDBCareer @ JobsDBInternational partnersBjobs (Bangladesh)Catho (Brazil)JobStreet (SE Asia)Jora (Hong Kong)JOCC Mundial (Mexico)Seaman 3c
Div Element Text: Bjobs (Bangladesh)Catho (Brazil)JobStreet (SE Asia)Jora (Hong Kong)JOCC Mundial (Mexico)Seaman Jobste (Philippines)SEEK (Australia)Work Ahead (Phil)
Div Element Text: Contact usPRTR@FacebookTwitter
Div Element Text: FacebookTwitter
Div Element Text: Privacy policyTerms & conditionsCopyright © 1998-2023, JobsDB
Scraping data from: https://th.jobsdb.com/th/en/job/senior-golang-engineer-300003002951973?token=0-4ef27b61-9c2f-4c69-96f7-271e4d4302&sectionRank=321&jobId=
Job 15
H1 Element Text: Senior Golang Engineer
Div Element Text: Job HighlightsSenior Golang EngineerInternational OrganizationAttractive Package & Career Growth
Div Element Text: Job DescriptionPRTR is looking to speak with a Senior Golang Engineer to work with a fast-growing global company based in Bangkok.Job DescriptionDevelo
Div Element Text: Additional InformationCareer LevelTopQualification(N/A)Years of Experience(N/A)Job TypePermanentCompany Websitehttp://www.ptc.com.th FunctionsInfomr
Div Element Text: Company OverviewMore than just a recruitment company. At PRTR, we have been a part of our customer's success for 30 years as their total HR solutions p
to develop a better career, a better life, and a better society, and thrive to become the No.1 people solutions organization in Southeast Asia.
http://www.ptc.com
PRTR | Thailand's Leading Provider of Total HR Solutions.
Div Element Text: Additional Company InformationIndustryHuman Resources Management/Consultancy
Div Element Text: Browse JobsPost resumesJob alertsProfileCareer adviceExplore careersExplore salariesDownload appsJobsDB @ App StoreJobsDB @ Google Play
Div Element Text: JobsDB @ App StoreJobsDB @ Google Play
Div Element Text: Post a job adSearch candidatesadvertise with usBest companies

```

Figure 5. Web scraping operation

3.2. Natural language processing

In research studies, NLP is a pivotal process where textual information takes center stage. This technology bridges the gap between human communication and computer understanding, facilitating sophisticated interactions that allow for the extraction and analysis of key information from vast amounts of text. Computers can interpret, manipulate, and comprehend human language in this step, converting unstructured text into easily analyzed structured data. The process encompasses several key steps, as outlined as follows [23].

3.2.1. Data cleaning and normalization

This step entails fundamental data cleaning, such as removing redundant words or words that have a negligible impact on the analysis. The objective is to streamline and normalize the dataset, ensuring that it is devoid of unnecessary elements that might hinder the effectiveness of subsequent analyses. To achieve this, it is essential to identify and eliminate any duplicates, irrelevant terms, or placeholder text that could obscure meaningful insights. The key technique in this step involves removing redundant and irrelevant words for processing, using commands in Excel to find unwanted words and replace them with blank values. This process helps to maintain the integrity and quality of the data. Figure 6 illustrates this method.

3.2.2. Punctuation removal

This step focuses on cleaning and normalizing the text by removing punctuation marks. We systematically eliminate elements such as punctuation, misspellings, symbols, and other textual characteristics that could impact processing. This step contributes to refining the dataset for enhanced accuracy and ease of subsequent processing. Punctuation marks such as (!"#\$%&*+,-./:;<=>@[^_`{|}) are specifically targeted for removal. In this step, the technique involves importing the regular expression and natural language toolkit (NLTK) libraries in Python [24] to manage unwanted characters. Figure 7 illustrates this.

Job Details
<p>Job Highlights Computing, Engineering, Information system System Analyst, Java Oracle Cloud, Oracle EBS, Fintech Job Description Job Summary: This role is responsible to provide maintenance, enhance new features on ServiceNow Platform. Monitor health, usage, and overall core experience in ERP (SAP), Dynamic 365, Oracle, CRM Problem solving in Application software to support Experience in programming Job Description Reporting to : Asst. General Manager – IT. Application Architect - Digital transformation Good interpersonal and communication skill Enterprise Architecture Integration Job Description Leading large organization companies based in Global Logistic Company, Good Career Opportunities Multi Cultural Environment, Yong & Fun Workplace BTS Onnut Location, Good Benefit Job Description Job Description : Gathering user requirements, analyze business requirements, design and develop software solutions. Job Highlights New Graduate or 0-2 years experience. Required GPAX equal or greater than 2.50. Able to program Java, VB.Net, C#, or Angular. Job Description Basic Salary = 31,000 THB / Month Work Location: Bangkok, Thailand. Job Highlights DevOps engineer, System engineer, Developer Database, Oracle, MySQL, MsSQL, PowerShell, Linux shell, AWS, Azure, GCP, Python Job Description Technology is changing every day and new graduates are welcome. Fixed Bonus Health insurance Job Description Coding Java or Python to enhance new features on ServiceNow Platform. Monitor health, usage, and overall core experience in ERP (SAP), Dynamic 365, Oracle, CRM Problem solving in Application software to support Experience in programming Job Description Reporting to : Asst. General Manager – IT. Application Architect - Digital transformation Good interpersonal and communication skill Enterprise Architecture Integration Job Description Leading large organization companies based in Global Logistic Company, Good Career Opportunities Multi Cultural Environment, Yong & Fun Workplace BTS Onnut Location, Good Benefit Job Description Job Description : Gathering user requirements, analyze business requirements, design and develop software solutions. Job Highlights New Graduate or 0-2 years experience. Required GPAX equal or greater than 2.50. Able to program Java, VB.Net, C#, or Angular. Job Description Basic Salary = 31,000 THB / Month Work Location: Bangkok, Thailand. Job Highlights DevOps engineer, System engineer, Developer Database, Oracle, MySQL, MsSQL, PowerShell, Linux shell, AWS, Azure, GCP, Python Job Description Technology is changing every day and new graduates are welcome. Fixed Bonus Health insurance Job Description Coding Java or Python to enhance new features on ServiceNow Platform. Monitor health, usage, and overall core experience in ERP (SAP), Dynamic 365, Oracle, CRM Problem solving in Application software to support Experience in programming Job Description Reporting to : Asst. General Manager – IT. Application Architect - Digital transformation Good interpersonal and communication skill Enterprise Architecture Integration Job Description Leading large organization companies based in Global Logistic Company, Good Career Opportunities Multi Cultural Environment, Yong & Fun Workplace BTS Onnut Location, Good Benefit Job Description Job Description : Gathering user requirements, analyze business requirements, design and develop software solutions. Job Highlights New Graduate or 0-2 years experience. Required GPAX equal or greater than 2.50. Able to program Java, VB.Net, C#, or Angular. Job Description Basic Salary = 31,000 THB / Month Work Location: Bangkok, Thailand. Job Highlights DevOps engineer, System engineer, Developer Database, Oracle, MySQL, MsSQL, PowerShell, Linux shell, AWS, Azure, GCP, Python Job Description Technology is changing every day and new graduates are welcome. Fixed Bonus Health insurance Job Description Coding Java or Python to enhance new features on ServiceNow Platform. Monitor health, usage, and overall core experience in ERP (SAP), Dynamic 365, Oracle, CRM Problem solving in Application software to support Experience in programming Job Description Reporting to : Asst. General Manager – IT. Application Architect - Digital transformation Good interpersonal and communication skill Enterprise Architecture Integration Job Description Leading large organization companies based in Global Logistic Company, Good Career Opportunities Multi Cultural Environment, Yong & Fun Workplace BTS Onnut Location, Good Benefit Job Description Job Description : Gathering user requirements, analyze business requirements, design and develop software solutions.</p>

Figure 6. Data cleaning and data normalization

<p>Technical Information Able to design application and coordinate with Vendor or other party Analyze Business Requirements and Assess Impact with Existing Database Architecture Through Understanding of Computer Architecture, Operating Systems, and Data Structures Write Clear and Detailed Technical Specifications and Document For any candidates who are interested in applying a job, please send CV with your recent photo in word or PDF format (.doc, .pdf) to our email via Apply Now: Vanness Plus Consulting Co., Ltd. Sathorn Square Building 98 North Sathorn Road, Silom, Bangrak, Bangkok 10500 Contact Person: Mr. Somchai Tel. 083-016-3160 Additional Information Career Level Middle Qualification Degree Years of Experience 1 year Job Type Full Time, Permanent, Temporary, Contract Job Functions Information Technology (IT), Support, Programming / Software Development, IT Consulting</p>	<p>Vendor or other party Analyze Business Requirements and Assess Impact with Existing Database Architecture Through Understanding of Computer Architecture Operating Systems and Data Structures Write Clear and Detailed Technical Specifications and Document For any candidates who are interested in applying a job please send CV with your recent photo in word or PDF format doc pdf to our email via Apply Now Vanness Plus Consulting Co Ltd Sathorn Square Building 98 North Sathorn Road Silom Bangrak Bangkok 10500 Contact Person Mr Somchai Tel 0830163160 Additional Information Career Level Middle Qualification Degree Years of Experience 1 year Job Type Full Time Permanent Temporary Contract Job Functions Information Technology IT Support Programming Software Development IT Consulting Additional Company Information Industry Human Resources Management Consultancy Benefits Others Free shuttle bus Medical insurance Overtime pay Five day work week</p>
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Figure 7. Punctuation removal operation

3.2.3. Tokenization

In this step, words undergo tokenization, a process that involves word segmentation and the removal of stop words. Tokenization breaks down the text into individual words, systematically eliminating stop words that can introduce noise in machine learning applications. We remove these superfluous terms, which we consider the cacophony of the text, to enhance the clarity and relevance of the analysis.

Notably, the removal of stop words contributes to obtaining meaningful nouns related to the job, streamlining the dataset by reducing the number of words. The tokenization process, which includes stop word removal, is executed using the Python NLTK and PyThaiNLP libraries, and custom additional stop words are incorporated to cater to the nuances of the Thai language [25]–[27]. Once we tokenize the text into words, we store the words in a Pandas data frame and export them to an Excel file for use in subsequent processes. As depicted in Figure 8.

3.2.4. Feature extraction

Feature extraction is a crucial step that involves studying job requirements based on the frequency of job positions. This analysis helps identify the most demanded skills and roles in the industry, which is particularly important for understanding employment trends and needs. We showcase the prominence of specific terms by creating a bag of words or a word cloud, which allows for a visual representation of key skills and requirements [28]. The research's results section will present the results of this feature extraction process, offering valuable insights into recurring job positions and their significance in the digital industry. This data is essential for organizations aiming to align their hiring strategies with market demands and for job seekers looking to enhance their qualifications in targeted areas.

16 custom_english_stopwords = ["year","years","a","able","about","above","abroad","abst","accordance", App Corporation IT MySQL Sathorn across cloud expansion looking
 "accordingly","across","act","actually","added","adj","adopted","affected","affecting","affects","after App Corporation IT NOW Sathorn across cloud expected looking
 "afterwards","again","against","ago","ah","ahead","ain't","all","allow","allows","almost","alone","ak App Create IT NS Sathorn across cloud experience looking
 "alongside","already","also","although","always","am","amid","amidst","among","amongst","amount App Cultural IT NS Sathorn actions coaching experience looking
 "announce","another","any","anybody","anyhow","anymore","anyone","anything","anyway","app Customer IT NS Science ad activitedesign code experience made
 "apart","apparently","appear","appreciate","appropriate","approximately","are","aren't","arent","aren't App Cyber IT NS Science ad code experience main
 "around","as","a's","aside","ask","asking","associated","at","auth","available","away","awfully","b App DB IT NS Science adSearch code experience main
 "backward","backwards","be","became","because","become","becomes","becoming","been","before App DB IT Netbeans Science adSearch code experience maintain
 "begin","beginning","beginnings","begins","behind","being","believe","below","beside","besides","be App DBA IT Network Science adSearch code experience maintain
 "better","between","beyond","bill","bill","both","bottom","brief","briefly","but","by","c","ca","call App DBA IT New Science adSearch code experience maintain
 "came","can","cannot","cant","can't","caption","cause","causes","certain","certainly","changes","cle App DBMSExperience IT New Science adSearch code experience maintain
 "c'mon","co","co.","com","come","comes","computer","con","concerning","consequently","consider App DNS IT New Science adSearch code experience maintaining
 "contain","containing","contains","corresponding","could","couldn't","couldn't","course","cry","c's", App Data ITL Navigen Science adSearch codebase experience maintaining
 "d","dare","daren't","date","de","definitely","describe","described","despite","detail","did","didn't App Data ITL Nippon Science adSearch coding experience maintaining
 "different","directly","do","does","doesn't","doing","done","don't","down","downwards","due","durin App Data ITSM No Science adSearch coding experience maintainingExper
 "each","ed","edu","effect","eg","eight","eighty","either","eleven","else","elsewhere","empty","end App Data identify No Science adSearch coding experience maintenance
 "enough","entirely","especially","et","et-al","etc","even","ever","evermore","every","everybody","ev App Data if No Science adSearch collaborate experience maintenance
 "everything","everywhere","ex","exactly","example","except","f","fairly","far","farther","few","fewer App Database if Node Science adSearch collaborate experience maintenance
 "fifteen","fifth","fifty","fill","find","fire","first","five","fix","followed","following","follows","for App Database impact Node ScopeThe adSearch code experience majoring
 "forever","former","formerly","forth","forty","forward","found","four","from","front","full","further App Database in NodeJS Score adSearch collaboration experience make
 "furthermore","g","gave","get","gets","getting","give","given","gives","giving","go","goes","going", App Database in NodeJS Script adSearch collaborative experience make
 "each","ed","edu","effect","eg","eight","eighty","either","eleven","else","elsewhere","empty","end App DatabaseJwelonin NodeJS Script adSearch collect experience makes
 "enough","entirely","especially","et","et-al","etc","even","ever","evermore","every","everybody","ev App Days Industrial North ScriptingGood adapt collecting experience making
 "everything","everywhere","ex","exactly","example","except","f","fairly","far","farther","few","fewer App Degree Information Not Sea address combination experienceRequi manage
 "fifteen","fifth","fifty","fill","find","fire","first","five","fix","followed","following","follows","for App Degree Information NowVanness Securities administrator combine experienced managed
 "forever","former","formerly","forth","forty","forward","found","four","from","front","full","further App Degree Information OOP Security administration come experiences management
 "furthermore","g","gave","get","gets","getting","give","given","gives","giving","go","goes","going", App Degree Information adopt security command command management
 "furthermore","g","gave","get","gets","getting","give","given","gives","giving","go","goes","going", App Degree Informationable Offera Security adopting command experiences management

Figure 8. Tokenization, word segmentation, and stop word removal operation

4. RESULTS

This study organizes its results into two primary segments: the first part analyzes job positions, highlighting the frequency and types of roles that are currently in demand. This section aims to highlight emerging trends and potential growth areas within the industry. The second part delves into the examination of workforce qualifications and requirements, assessing the specific skills and educational backgrounds employers are seeking. This analysis is crucial for understanding the alignment between job market demands and available workforce capabilities. The subsequent sections provide detailed insights into each facet of the study, offering a comprehensive overview that can inform stakeholders, including policymakers, educators, and industry leaders, in their decision-making processes.

4.1. Results of job positions

The study revealed numerous job positions with distinct requirements. To provide a comprehensive overview, we present the top 10 most common job positions within the digital industry, as outlined in Table 1. In addition to highlighting the most prevalent job positions in the digital industry sector, Table 1 serves as a crucial tool for understanding the core competencies and skills most valued in these roles. By analyzing these positions, we can discern the dynamic nature of the digital job market and the specific expertise that employers prioritize. This insight is vital for both job seekers aiming to enhance their careers and organizations striving to recruit the best talent in a competitive environment.

Examining job positions within the digital industry has revealed prevalent roles across several sectors. These include Electrical Engineers in hardware and smart devices, who design and develop new electronic equipment; Programmers in software and software services, who write and test code for various applications; IT support specialists in digital services, who maintain and troubleshoot information systems; graphic designers in digital content, who create engaging visual content; and network engineers in telecommunications, who construct and manage vital communication networks. These positions are in high demand across the job market, indicating a strong and ongoing need for a skilled workforce in these areas. Individuals with expertise in these domains are well-equipped to find stable and rewarding employment in the rapidly evolving digital industry [29].

Table 1. The most common job positions

No.	Hardware and smart device	Software and software service	Digital service	Digital content	Telecommunication
1	Electrical engineer	Programmer	IT support	Graphic design	Network engineer
2	Sales engineer	System analyst	Digital marketing	Creative	Telecommunications technician
3	Production engineer	Web developer	Application support	UX/UI design	Technical support
4	Network engineer	Full stack developer	Business analyst	Content creator	Production engineer
5	System engineer	Mobile app developer	Project manager	Video editor	Project engineer
6	Project engineer	System engineer	Data analyst	Tiktok content creator	Engineer specialist WAN
7	Service engineer	Software tester	Data engineer	Photographer	Service engineer
8	Maintenance engineer	Software developer	IT project management	Web designer	Signaling deliver engineer
9	IT support	Backend developer	Enterprise resource planning (ERP)	Video content creator	System engineer
10	Network operation center	Software engineer	Cloud engineer	Digital content creator	Communications specialist

4.2. Results of workforce requirements

The study looked into workforce qualifications based on job market demands within each digital industry group. This comprehensive analysis encompassed a range of criteria, including education level, skills, specialization, experience, and technological proficiency. To provide a broad perspective, we present the top 10 requirements that are most in demand, as outlined in Table 2. Table 2 not only sheds light on the key qualifications sought after in the digital industry but also emphasizes the evolving nature of these demands as the sector adapts to new technologies and market trends. The findings provide valuable insights for prospective workers seeking to align their career paths with market needs, as well as educational institutions seeking to update their curricula to better prepare students for future job opportunities.

Table 2. The most common qualifications and requirements

No.	Hardware and smart device	Software and software service	Digital service	Digital content	Telecommunication
1	Bachelor degree	Bachelor degree	Bachelor degree	Bachelor degree	Bachelor degree
2	Experience	Web development	Project manager	Graphic design	Telecommunication technical Maintenance
3	Engineering	Mobile application development	Software service	Social media content	
4	Customers	Software development	Customers service	Creative content	Vocational certificate
5	English skills	Technical support	English skills	Digital media	Electrical engineering
6	Electrical	System design	Data engineer	Advertising and Marketing	Customers service
7	Network	Advertising and Marketing	Customers service	Adobe Photoshop	English skills
8	Management	SQL database	Communication	Communication	Equipment skill
9	Technical	Project manager	Knowledge	English skills	Sales experience
10	Support	Software tester	Support	Adobe Premiere Pro	Products

Across all five industrial groups, the study on qualifications and workforce requirements reveals that educational qualifications are the primary prerequisites for workers, with a strong preference for individuals who have completed a bachelor's degree. Subsequently, deep knowledge, specialized abilities, and job-specific skills or functional competencies are of significant importance in securing employment in these sectors. Moreover, employers frequently seek out various other requirements, including the ability to work outside, availability for overtime, and proficiency in English. These findings underscore the holistic nature of the qualifications demanded in the digital industry, highlighting not only the technical skills but also the adaptability and soft skills that are critical for success. This comprehensive understanding helps guide job seekers in their career development efforts and assists educational institutions in tailoring their programs to meet the evolving demands of the workforce.

4.3. Results of natural language processing

The NLP phase's outcomes include word frequency analysis using the bag-of-words (BoW) technique and the creation of a word cloud for text feature extraction using Python. These results play a pivotal role in enhancing the understanding of textual data, offering a visual representation of the frequency and prominence of specific terms. We generate the word cloud using Python libraries like matplotlib and wordcloud to visually emphasize these frequencies [30], highlighting the most critical and frequently mentioned terms in an impactful and easily digestible format. The subsequent sections delve into the insights gained from these NLP analyses, providing a nuanced interpretation of the language used in the digital industry workforce requirements. This comprehensive approach aids stakeholders in aligning their strategies with the industry's actual needs by identifying key trends, common qualifications, and highly valued skills.

4.3.1. Job position analysis of Group 1

According to the word frequency analysis of job positions within digital industry Group 1, which focuses on hardware and smart devices, the top positions are as follows: i) electrical engineer (92 positions), ii) sales engineer (92 positions), and iii) production engineer (71 positions). Figure 9 depicts these positions and various others, offering a clear visual representation of the frequency distribution of job positions within this industry group. This visualization not only highlights the most in-demand roles but also illustrates the diversity of career opportunities available within the sector. Understanding these trends helps stakeholders, such as job seekers and educational institutions, align their goals and curricula with the industry's needs, ensuring they are preparing for the most prevalent and emerging roles.

5. DISCUSSION

The study of requirements for the digital industry workforce identified significant needs across five groups: i) In the hardware and smart devices group, the most required position is that of an electrical engineer; ii) Programmer is the most sought-after job title in the software and software services group; iii) In the digital service group, IT support is the most in-demand; iv) Within digital content, the role of graphic designer is most needed; and v) In the telecommunications group, the role of network engineer is highly sought after. Additionally, all industry groups require the workforce to have a bachelor's degree as a foundational skill.

However, when compared with previous studies, it appears that no research has yet clearly presented both the job positions and skill requirements demanded by the labor market. As a result, the findings of this study are beneficial for the workforce seeking employment in the digital industry, as they provide insights into the necessary skills for preparation and competition for the desired job positions. This new knowledge empowers the workforce to strategically position themselves within the competitive landscape of the digital industry, enhancing their employability and readiness to meet future challenges.

6. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this research represents a systematic inquiry into the employment prerequisites of the digital industry, using web scraping and NLP techniques to provide valuable insights into job roles and requisite qualifications. The study's findings significantly contribute to the research topic by offering a detailed understanding of industry expectations, which is essential for both individuals aiming to enter the digital field and educational institutions striving to align their curricula with market needs. The positive impact of this research lies in its ability to bridge the gap between academia and the professional world, ensuring that graduates are well-equipped to meet the challenges and leverage the opportunities of the digital industry.

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